

Molar Volume and Viscosity of Magnesium Acetate in Aqueous Acetic Acid

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The apparent molar volume, ϕ_v and viscosity of magnesium acetate has been determined in 10, 20, 30 and 40% aqueous acetic acid at different temperatures. Results have been interpreted in terms of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions and structure-making/structure-breaking capacity from $(\delta^2 \phi_{v0}/\delta t^2)$ and dB/dT values. The values of $\Delta\mu_2^{\circ\ddagger}$ and $\Delta\mu_1^{\circ\ddagger}$ for viscous flows from transition state theory and ϕ_{E0} , i.e. apparent molar expansibility have also been determined. Magnesium acetate has been found to be the structure-promoter from molar volume as well as viscosity studies.

THE study of apparent molar volumes of electrolytes at infinite dilution, B parameter of the Jones-Dole equation^{1,2} for viscosity and their dependence on temperature can furnish useful information on the nature of solute-solvent interactions. Blokhra *et al.* studied acetates of lithium and sodium in aqueous methyl acetate^{1,2} and ammonium salts in aqueous acetic acid³ from the viewpoint of solute-solvent interaction. In all the cases the stress was laid on 1 : 1 electrolytes in binary solvent. In the present communication studies with magnesium acetate in aqueous acetic acid are described. Magnesium acetate in aqueous acetic acid was selected because it has common ion with solvent and solute having common ion with solvent may produce interesting results from both theoretical and experimental viewpoints of solution chemistry. In order to know about the nature of the solute-solvent interaction, molar volume and viscosity of magnesium acetate in aqueous acetic acid were determined and discussed in the present communication.

Experimental

Water used for solutions had specific conductance in the range $0.1-1.0 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Magnesium acetate (G.R.) was dried in vacuum desiccator. Acetic acid was of G.R. grade. All the solutions were prepared by weight and conversion of molality to molarity was carried out by the expression given elsewhere⁴. Density was determined with the help of apparatus as described by Ward and Millero⁵. Viscosity was determined with the help of a capillary type viscometer⁶.

Results and Discussion

The apparent molar volume has been calculated from density data by using equation (1)⁷,

$$\phi_v = \frac{M_2}{d_0} - \frac{1000(d-d_0)}{md_0} \quad (1)$$

where, d_0 is the density of solvent, d the density of solution, m the molarity of solution and M_2 the molecular weight of the salt.

Errors in ϕ_v were calculated from equation (2)⁸,

$$\Delta \phi_v = (2\Delta d/d^2)(1000/m + M_2) \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) assumes errors to be associated with the density of solution (d) and solvent (d_0). Moreover, errors associated with determination of solution concentration are not the limiting factor while calculating the apparent molar volumes. The errors as derived from equation (2) was estimated to range from $\pm 0.01 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at $0.01 M$ concentration to $\pm 0.13 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at $0.12 M$ concentration.

Limiting apparent molar volume has been calculated with the help of Redlich and Meyer's equation⁷,

$$\frac{\phi_v - \phi_{v0}}{\sqrt{m}} = S_v + b_v \sqrt{m} \quad (3)$$

The plots of $(\phi_v - \phi_{v0})/\sqrt{m}$ vs \sqrt{m} were adjusted for different values of ϕ_{v0} in order to have best-fit. Approximate value for ϕ_{v0} , however, was taken from plot of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{m} . The values of limiting molar volume, slope and intercept are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—LIMITING APPARENT MOLAR VOLUME ϕ_{v0} , S_v AND b_v FOR MAGNESIUM ACETATE IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Acetic acid %	Temp. °C	ϕ_{v0} $\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	S_v $\text{cm}^3 \text{ l}^{1/2} \text{ mol}^{-3/2}$	b_v $\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-3/2} \text{ l}$
10.00	303.0	123.4 ± 0.03	105.9 ± 0.31	-9.50 ± 1.56
20.00	303.0	181.9 ± 0.10	-136.9 ± 1.24	-28.12 ± 4.13
30.00	303.0	176.1 ± 0.02	-133.5 ± 0.38	-9.53 ± 1.92
40.00	303.0	119.9 ± 0.02	75.5 ± 0.21	-13.80 ± 0.31
10.00	298.0	114.2 ± 0.01	78.6 ± 0.13	2.69 ± 0.72
10.00	308.0	135.0 ± 0.01	67.4 ± 0.12	14.39 ± 1.07
10.00	313.0	147.0 ± 0.02	-112.6 ± 0.18	50.89 ± 0.96

The intercept S_v in Redlich equation may be attributed to be a measure of ion-ion or solute-solute interaction. It is obvious from the sign of S_v that ion-ion interaction is strong in 10 and 40% acetic acid but weak in 20 and 30% acetic acid. In 10% acetic acid at 298, 303 and 308 K ion-ion interaction is strong but it is weak at 313 K. With the increase in temperature ion-ion interaction first increases reaching maximum at 303 K and then decreases. The change of sign of S_v with temperature and with percentage of acetic acid may be due to changes in structural aspect of the solvent medium by magnesium acetate and change in the extent of solvation of Mg^{2+} ions. The empirical constant b_v seems to be the function of concentration of solvent and temperature. It decreases with increasing content of acetic acid having a maximum decrease at 20% acetic acid, however, it increases with temperature.

ϕ_{v0} is a measure of solute-solvent interaction. Its magnitude is positive and large in all the cases thereby suggesting strong solute-solvent interactions. ϕ_{v0} first increases with increasing percent of acetic acid and attains a maxima. The continuous decrease in ϕ_{v0} with percent of acetic acid may not be considered to lead to zero solute-solvent interaction with increased concentration of acetic acid. Solute-solvent interaction may decrease due to the establishment of ionic equilibrium in solvent system. It may also be attributed to the dissociation constant of magnesium acetate which is about 0.1 in water, and to the lowering of dielectric constant with addition of acetic acid. ϕ_{v0} increases with increase in temperature showing more and more solute-solvent interaction which may be due to the increase in solvation. The temperature dependence of ϕ_{v0} in 10% acetic acid can be expressed by the equation,

$$|\phi_{v0}| \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} = -3.442 - 1.185t + 0.0053t^2 \quad (4)$$

where, t is the temperature in degrees celsius.

The apparent molar expansibility, $\phi_{E0} = (\delta^2 \phi_{v0} / \delta t^2)$ calculated from equation (4) has been to increase with temperature (Table 2). The increase in expansibility shows that magnesium acetate in aqueous acetic acid (10%) behave like symmetrical tetraalkylammonium salts⁹ and also like magnesium chloride and magnesium sulphate in aqueous sodium bicarbonate¹⁰. The positive increase of ϕ_{E0} with temperature may be attributed to the caging effect⁹.

TABLE 2—APPARENT MOLAR EXPANSIBILITY (ϕ_{E0}) OF MAGNESIUM ACETATE IN 10% AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. (T) K	ϕ_{E0} $\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
298.0	1.97
303.0	2.03
308.0	2.08
313.0	2.13

The structure-making capacity of magnesium acetate was deduced with the help of Hepler's reasoning¹¹, i.e. on the basis of the sign of $(\delta^2 \phi_{v0} / \delta t^2)_P$. It has been deduced from general thermodynamic equation :

$$(\delta \bar{C}_P / \delta P)_T = -(\delta^2 \phi_{v0} / \delta t^2)_P \quad (5)$$

From equation (5) a structure-making solute should have positive value of $(\delta^2 \phi_{v0} / \delta t^2)_P$. In case of magnesium acetate, $(\delta^2 \phi_{v0} / \delta t^2)_P$ has been found to be positive. This shows that magnesium acetate is structure-maker. Similar conclusions have been drawn from viscosity data analysis on the basis of Jones-Dole equation¹²,

$$\eta / \eta_0 = 1 + A \sqrt{m} + Bm \quad (6)$$

where, η and η_0 are viscosities of solution and solvent, respectively, m is molar concentration, and A and B are constants. The values of A and B have been determined from the intercept and slope of straight line plots of $(\eta / \eta_0 - 1) / \sqrt{m}$ vs \sqrt{m} . These values of different solutions are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF PARAMETERS OF JONES-DOLE EQUATION

Acetic acid %	Temp. (T) K	A (l mol^{-1}) ¹³	B l mol^{-1}
10.00	303.0	-0.012 ± 0.024	+1.27 ± 0.123
20.00	303.0	+0.080 ± 0.014	+1.10 ± 0.077
30.00	303.0	+0.108 ± 0.012	+0.62 ± 0.061
40.00	303.0	+0.124 ± 0.020	+1.50 ± 0.092
10.00	298.0	-0.032 ± 0.026	+1.07 ± 0.142
10.00	308.0	+0.052 ± 0.023	+0.77 ± 0.118
10.00	313.0	+0.144 ± 0.014	+0.60 ± 0.077

Parameter A of Jones-Dole equation represents the contribution from solute-solute interaction¹³. Positive A values indicate solute-solute interaction. But negative A values in 10% aqueous acetic acid at 298 and 303 K cannot be explained on the basis of Falkenhagen theory, and according to this theory, the negative values of A in a given solvent system may be without any physical significance¹⁴. A values, however, increase with increase in acetic acid as well as temperature. The B parameter which measures the structure-making/-breaking capacity of an electrolyte¹⁴ in a solution also contains a contribution from structural effects, and is responsible for solute-solvent interaction in a solvent¹⁵.

It has been emphasised by a number of workers that dB/dT is more important criterion¹⁶ for determining solute-solvent interaction, as positive B coefficient obtained from aqueous solutions can be interpreted as being merely due to large size ion. Viscosity study of a number of salts has shown that structure-makers will have negative dB/dT . The temperature effect on magnesium acetate solution in 10% aqueous acetic acid at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K

shows a negative sign of dB/dT showing thereby that magnesium acetate behaves as structure-maker.

Transition state theory of the relative viscosities of electrolytic solutions as suggested by Feakins *et al.*¹⁷ gives rise to equation (7),

$$B = \frac{\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0}{1000} + \frac{\bar{V}_1^0}{1000} \left| \frac{\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}}{RT} \right| \quad (7)$$

where, \bar{V}_1^0 and \bar{V}_2^0 are the limiting partial molar volumes of the solvent and solute, respectively, $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ is the free energy of activation per mole for viscous flows of solution, and $\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$ the free energy of activation per mole of pure solvent is given by equation (8)¹⁸,

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger} = \Delta G_1^\ddagger = RT \ln (\eta_0 \bar{V}_1^0 / hN) \quad (8)$$

where, h is Planck constant. N the Avogadro number and η_0 the viscosity of solvent.

Equation (7) may also be written as

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger} = \mu_1^{0\ddagger} + \frac{RT}{\bar{V}_1^0} \left| 1000 B - (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0) \right| \quad (9)$$

The data was also analysed in the light of above treatment of transition state theory. $\bar{V}_2^0 = \phi_{v0}$ used was the same as from molar volume studies (Table 1) and \bar{V}_1^0 has been found to be 60.20 cm³ mol⁻¹ at 303 K experimentally. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ are recorded in Table 4. $\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$ seems to be constant all over the selected solvent range. However, a very slight change in it has been observed with solvent composition at 303 K.

The quantity $(\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger})$ is the change in activation energy per mole of solute on replacing one mole of solvent by one mole of solute at infinite dilute solution. The magnitude of $(\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger})$ is found to be positive showing that on addition of solute to solvent, the solute acts as structure-promoter¹⁷. $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ and hence the magnitude of $(\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger})$ is maximum at 40% aqueous acetic acid showing that flow is least favoured at this

TABLE 4—VALUES OF \bar{V}_2^0 , $\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$ AND $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID AT 303 K

Acetic acid	\bar{V}_2^0 ml mol ⁻¹	$\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ kJ mol ⁻¹
10 00	128 4	5 76	18 99
20 00	181 9	5 86	16 96
30 00	176 1	5 95	18 13
40 00	119 9	6 03	21.53

solvent composition as compared to other compositions at 303 K.

Conclusion : From the results obtained in the present study following conclusion have been drawn : (i) the data of apparent molar volumes at different concentration can be represented by Redlich and Meyer's equation, (ii) the ion-ion interactions decreases with increase in temperature, (iii) the decrease in solute-solvent interaction with increasing concentration of acetic acid is due to the establishment of ionic-equilibrium in the solvent and to the dissociation of magnesium acetate in water, (iv) the increase in expansibility with temperature has been attributed to the caging effect, and (v) viscous studies show that magnesium acetate behave as structure-maker in aqueous acetic acid, which has been explained from the viewpoint of Feakin's theory of transition state theory as applied to viscous behaviour of electrolytic solutions.

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